

Optical Properties and Electronic Structures of Intrinsic Gapped Metals: Inverse Materials Design Principles for Transparent Conductors

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Abstract: Traditional solid-state physics has long correlated the optical properties of materials with their electronic structures. However, recent discoveries of intrinsic gapped metals have challenged this classical view. Gapped metals possess electronic properties distinct from both metals and insulators, with a large concentration of free carriers without any intentional doping and an internal band gap. This unique electronic structure makes gapped metals potentially superior to materials designed by intentional doping of the wide band gap insulators. Despite their promising applications, such as transparent conductors, designing gapped metals for specific purposes remains challenging due to the lack of understanding of the correlation between their electronic band structures and optical properties. This study focuses on representative examples of gapped metals and demonstrates the cases of (i) gapped metals (e.g., CaN_2) with strong intraband absorption in the visible range, (ii) gapped metals (e.g., SrNbO_3) with strong interband absorption in the visible range, (iii) gapped metals (e.g., $\text{Sr}_5\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{17}$) that are potential transparent conductors. We explore the complexity of identifying potential gapped metals for transparent conductors and propose inverse materials design principles for discovering new-generation transparent conductors.

25 In recent years, there has been a growing interest in understanding and manipulating the optical
26 properties of materials for various technological applications, ranging from optoelectronics and
27 photovoltaics to sensing and quantum computing¹⁻³. Traditional solid-state physics books^{4, 5} teach us
28 that the optical properties of a material are defined by its electronic structure. For instance, wide band
29 gap insulators are transparent due to the large energy band gaps (over 3.2 eV) between their principal
30 valence and conduction bands, which prevents visible light from exciting electrons from occupied to
31 unoccupied states⁶⁻⁸. In contrast, metals are opaque due to the continuous nature of their electronic
32 structure, resulting in strong band-to-band transitions and free carrier absorption^{9, 10}. This correlation
33 between electronic structure and optical properties allows us to use the color of a compound as an
34 indicator of its conductivity. For example, in semiconductors, the band gap is smaller than in insulators,
35 allowing for the absorption of photons with shorter wavelengths, resulting in a colored sample^{11, 12}.

36 Recent studies¹³⁻²⁰ have challenged this classical picture by revealing the existence of intrinsic gapped
37 metals that possess electronic properties distinct from both metals and insulators. Specifically, these
38 materials have a Fermi level in the conduction or valence band, resulting in a large concentration of
39 free carriers without intentional doping but with an internal band gap between their principal band
40 edges. This unique electronic structure makes gapped metals potentially superior compared to
41 materials designed through intentional doping of wide band gap insulators, as gapped metals are not
42 subject to the limitation of doping bottleneck (i.e., Fermi level pinning or defect clustering, restricting
43 the ability to modify material's electronic properties through intentional doping)^{13, 21}. In addition, these
44 material features make gapped metals potentially useful for various applications. For instance, Irvine
45 et al.²² discovered that metallic SrNbO₃ could be used for photocatalysis, Hosono et al.²³ reported the
46 first solid-state electride gapped metal, while Zunger et al.¹⁴ demonstrated that intrinsic gapped metals
47 could be transparent conductors.

48 However, it is important to note that designing gapped metals for specific applications, such as
49 transparent conductors, is not a straightforward task due to the lack of understanding regarding the
50 correlation between their electronic band structures and optical properties. In particular, the criteria
51 for selecting the appropriate atomic identities, composition, and structure to achieve the desired
52 optoelectronic functionality is often uncertain. This uncertainty arises from the complex interplay of
53 free carrier absorption and interband transition, which together define the optical properties of the
54 gapped metals, making a comprehensive understanding of the essential step of the material design. To
55 address this, we focus on representative examples of gapped metals and identify three principal types
56 of intrinsic gapped metals based on their electronic structures (see discussion below). These
57 classifications help shed light on the underlying mechanisms governing the optical properties of these
58 materials, which in turn help to establish the design principles for potential transparent conductors and
59 provide a systematic approach to the discovery of new materials, taking into account the complex
60 interplay of factors that determine the properties of gapped metals.

61 The optical properties of gapped metals are defined by the superposition of interband transition and
62 the Drude contribution. The latter is characterized by the ratio of carrier concentration (n) and effective
63 mass (m^*) defining plasma frequencies (i.e., $\omega_p \sim \sqrt{n/m^*}$). When the ratio is large, free carrier
64 absorption makes the material opaque, even if it has a large internal band gap. This behavior is
65 exemplified by the experimentally synthesized CaN₂ compound (space group (SG): 139), which is known

66 as a colored metal^{24, 25}. Specifically, our density functional theory (DFT) calculations show that CaN₂ is
 67 a nonmagnetic n-type gapped metal with the Fermi level in the principal conduction band and a band
 68 gap (we note that we use Perdew-Becke-Ernzerhof (PBE)²⁶ exchange-correlation (XC) functional, which
 69 usually underestimates internal band gap energy²⁷, but is not expected to change the physics presented
 70 in this work, see examples in Refs.^{17, 28}) of 2.84 eV between principal band edges (Fig. 1a,b). The
 71 principal valence and conduction bands are dominated by N-p orbitals. The Fermi level is located 2.84
 72 eV above the principal conduction band minimum, indicating that the transition between occupied and
 73 unoccupied states within the conduction band cannot be neglected. The optical properties of materials
 74 show the presence of strong band-to-band transitions even at low frequencies, which is consistent with
 75 the point above, especially taking into account that the energy of the first direct transition (calculated
 76 from band structure, Fig. 1b) between occupied states in the principal valence band and unoccupied
 77 states in the conduction band is 6.01 eV (Fig. 1c,d). Due to large free carrier concentration (i.e., 5.1×10^{22}
 78 e/cm^3 corresponding to number of electrons in the principal conduction band), CaN₂ has a large
 79 unscreened anisotropic plasma frequency, i.e., $\omega_p^{xx} \approx 4.6$ eV, $\omega_p^{yy} \approx 4.6$ eV, and $\omega_p^{zz} \approx 6.82$ eV, which is
 80 clearly reflected in real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function (Fig. 1c). This is not surprising, as,
 81 by textbook definition (we note that a more generalized expression is actually used in DFT²⁹), the Drude
 82 contribution to $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ and $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ can be expressed as $\epsilon_2(\omega) = \frac{\gamma \omega_p^2}{\omega(\omega^2 + \gamma^2)}$ and $\epsilon_1(\omega) = 1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{(\omega^2 + \gamma^2)}$,
 83 respectively, where γ is the damping coefficient. These expressions explicitly suggest that the Drude
 84 contribution has a substantial effect on the low-frequency region, which approaches the asymptotic
 85 value as frequency increases. This is shown in supplementary materials for all compounds discussed in
 86 this paper (Figs. S1-S4). The results above clearly demonstrate that not all gapped metals are
 87 transparent conductors, and high carrier concentrations of free carriers, while much desired for high
 88 electronic conductivity, can reduce material transparency. While this type of gapped metal is not
 89 attractive for transparent conductor applications, it has distinct features for other optoelectronic
 90 applications, including, for instance, crossing the real part of the dielectric function and strong
 91 plasmonic contribution. We also note that, in general, the properties of such materials can still be tuned
 92 if there is a way to control the free carrier concentration or effective mass by an external knob. For
 93 instance, we previously showed that the properties of gapped metals, in general, can be controlled via
 94 controllable spontaneous off-stoichiometry^{15, 28, 30} or strain²⁰.

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 98 **Figure 1. Gapped metals with strong intraband absorption in the visible range.** (a) The bulk Brillouin zone for CaN₂ in
 99 tetragonal (I4/mmm, SG: 139) symmetry with several high-symmetry k -points $\Gamma(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)$, X(0.0, 0.0, 0.5), N(0.0, 0.5,
 100 0.0), Y(-0.18, 0.18, 0.5), $\Sigma(-0.34, 0.34, 0.34)$, P(0.25, 0.25, 0.25), Z(0.5, 0.5, -0.5), Y1(0.5, 0.5, -0.18) and $\Sigma 1(0.34, 0.66, -$
 101 $0.34)$ ³¹. The red lines highlight the high symmetry k -path and (b) the calculated electronic band structure along the high
 102 symmetry k -paths for CaN₂ using PBE functional. Here, the dotted line corresponds to the Fermi level, the internal band gap
 103 (E_g^{int}) is 2.84 eV, and the occupied part of conduction (ΔE_{CB}) is 2.84 eV. (c) Real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function
 104 and (d) absorption spectra of CaN₂ when both interband and intraband transitions are accounted for. The crystal structure
 105 of CaN₂ is shown as an inset.
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107 In traditional semiconductors, the absorption spectra of a material are usually defined by the direct
 108 transition from the valence to the conduction band (i.e., direct band gap energy) with phonon assistant
 109 absorption playing significantly smaller role³². In a defect-free world, for traditional insulators, the color
 110 of the material is directly related to the band gap energy, and materials transparency simply requires a
 111 large band gap. However, as already noted above, for gapped metals, due to the finite occupation of
 112 the conduction or valence band, the interband transition between principal band edges can only be
 113 observed at energies significantly higher than the direct band gap energy. This resembles the Burstein-
 114 Moss effect^{33, 34} in traditional wide-band-gap insulators that are self- or externally doped, and it further
 115 highlights the complexity of the optical properties of the gapped metals. We note, however, that
 116 interband transitions, even in a gapped metal, can define materials transparency. To demonstrate this,
 117 we consider the example of the NbCoSb half-Heusler compound (space group: $F\bar{4}3m$), which can be
 118 experimentally synthesized using, for instance, arc melting method^{35, 36}. Here, for simplicity, we limit
 119 our investigation to stoichiometric NbCoSb compound, even though the degree of off-stoichiometry
 120 can be significant in this type of materials^{36, 37}. Our DFT calculations show that NbCoSb is an example of

121 n-type nonmagnetic gapped metal having the Fermi level in the conduction band, a large density of free
 122 carriers $1.9 \times 10^{22} \text{ e/cm}^3$, and an internal band gap of 0.93 eV between principal band edges (this internal
 123 band gap energy may be underestimated due to the using the PBE functional). Here, the conduction
 124 band is occupied within the 0.64 eV energy range. The first direct transition between the occupied
 125 principal valence band and unoccupied states in the principal conduction band is observed at 1.83 eV,
 126 implying a strong band-to-band transition in the visible range. The transparency of the material is also
 127 affected by the strong Drude contribution, the plasma frequency tensor is isotropic with a plasma
 128 frequency of 3.65 eV.

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 130 **Figure 2. Gapped metals with strong interband absorption in the visible range.** (a) The bulk Brillouin zone for NbCoSb in
 131 cubic ($F\bar{4}3m$, SG: 216) symmetry with several high-symmetry k -points $\Gamma(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)$, $X(0.5, 0.0, 0.5)$, $W(0.5, 0.25, 0.75)$,
 132 $K(0.375, 0.375, 0.75)$, $U(0.625, 0.25, 0.625)$, and $L(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$ ³¹. The red lines highlight the high symmetry k -path and (b)
 133 the calculated electronic band structure along the high symmetry k -paths for NbCoSb using PBE functional. Here, the dotted
 134 line corresponds to the Fermi level, the internal band gap (E_g^{int}) is 0.93 eV, and the occupied part of conduction (ΔE_{CB}) is
 135 0.64 eV. (c) Real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function and (d) absorption spectra of NbCoSb when both interband
 136 and intraband transitions are accounted for. The crystal structure of NbCoSb is shown as an inset.

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 138 To further understand this type of compound, we consider SrNbO_3 gapped metal^{22, 38}, which is known
 139 to have distinct color experimentally (we note that experimentally this compound is often reported to
 140 be off-stoichiometric, however, for simplicity, we use the stoichiometric form here). Our calculations
 141 demonstrate that this compound has the Fermi level in the principal conduction band with a large
 142 internal band gap of 2.51 eV and free carrier concentration of $1.5 \times 10^{22} \text{ e/cm}^3$. These results suggest
 143 that transitions from occupied states of the principal valence band to the principal conduction band are
 144 not activated until 3.81 eV (energy of first direct transition). Despite this, due to large free carrier

145 concentration, there is still strong absorption in the visible range from the superposition of the
 146 transition from occupied to unoccupied states in the principal conduction band and strong Drude
 147 contribution caused by anisotropic plasma frequency contribution (i.e., $\omega_p^{xx} \approx 4.35$ eV, $\omega_p^{yy} \approx 4.39$ eV,
 148 and $\omega_p^{zz} \approx 5.02$ eV). These results thus show that having a large internal gap in gaped metal is not
 149 sufficient for making material to be a transparent conductor, and indeed transition between occupied
 150 and unoccupied states in the conduction band can noticeably reduce the materials transparency (we
 151 note, however, that both materials discussed herein in addition to interband transition also have a
 152 strong intraband transition, see supporting information).

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 154 **Figure 3. Gapped metals with strong interband absorption in the visible range.** (a) The bulk Brillouin zone for SrNbO₃ in
 155 orthorhombic (Pnma, SG: 62) symmetry with several high-symmetry k-points $\Gamma(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)$, X(0.5, 0.0, 0.0), R(0.5, 0.5, 0.5),
 156 S(0.5, 0.5, 0.0), Y(0.0, 0.5, 0.0), Z(0.0, 0.0, 0.5), U(0.5, 0.0, 0.5), R(0.5, 0.5, 0.5), and T(0.0, 0.5, 0.5)^{31, 39}. The red lines highlight
 157 the high symmetry k-path and (b) the calculated electronic band structure along the high symmetry k-paths for SrNbO₃ using
 158 PBE functional. Here, the dotted line corresponds to the Fermi level, the internal band gap (E_g^{int}) is 0.93 eV, and the occupied
 159 part of conduction (ΔE_{CB}) is 0.64 eV. (c) Average real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function and (d) absorption spectra
 160 of SrNbO₃ when both interband and intraband transitions are accounted for. The crystal structure of SrNbO₃ is shown as an
 161 inset.
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163 The above results demonstrate that identification of the gapped metals that are both conductive and
 164 transparent is a complex task. Thus, the gapped metal as a transparent conductor should satisfy the
 165 following conditions: (i) the compound needs to be realizable, i.e., one that can be really synthesized in
 166 stoichiometric form (we note that indeed first principle literature is full of fantasy materials that cannot
 167 be realized^{40, 41}); (ii) the compound should have the free carrier concentration to provide sufficient
 168 electronic transport, however, this concentration should be not too large to not cause strong Drude

169 absorption is visible range making gapped metal to be opaque; (iii) the compound should have
170 minimized transition from occupied to unoccupied states in the visible range. To demonstrate the
171 example of such material, we consider the case of $\text{Sr}_5\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{17}$ n-type gapped metal, which was previously
172 prepared by the floating-zone melting technique and has been characterized by single-crystal X-ray
173 analysis to have an orthorhombic Pnm space group⁴². The principal valence band of the compound is
174 mainly determined by O-p states, while the principal conduction band is defined by Nb-d states. Our
175 PBE calculations show that the compound is a nonmagnetic n-type gapped metal that has 1e per f.u.
176 (i.e., $1.3 \times 10^{21} \text{ e/cm}^3$) in the principal conduction band, which is spread in 0.63 eV energy space, and the
177 large internal band gap energy of 2.3 eV. The first available direct transition from occupied states of
178 principal valence to unoccupied states of principal conduction band is 3.12 eV, resulting in band-to-
179 band transition from the principal valence to the principal conduction band within the visible range (Fig.
180 4). The free carrier concentration is large enough to provide sufficiently high electronic conductivity but
181 is low enough not to have strong free carrier absorption in the visible range. For instance, the
182 anisotropic plasma frequency tensor (i.e., $\omega_p^{xx} \approx 1.95 \text{ eV}$, $\omega_p^{yy} \approx 0.49 \text{ eV}$, and $\omega_p^{zz} \approx 0.11 \text{ eV}$) do not results
183 is substantial free carrier absorption. Hence, the resulted light absorption in the visible range is limited,
184 making $\text{Sr}_5\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{17}$ a potential transparent conductor. These results further demonstrate that, even
185 among compounds with identical chemical identities (e.g., Sr-Nb-O family), material transparency is
186 largely determined by the electronic structure. Thus, SrNbO_3 with high free carrier concentration has
187 strong Drude contribution and strong transition from occupied to unoccupied states within the
188 conduction band, resulting in a distinct color. In contrast, $\text{Sr}_5\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{17}$, with its significantly lower free
189 carrier concentration, is transparent.

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Figure 4. Gapped metals that are potential transparent conductors. (a) The bulk Brillouin zone for $Sr_5Nb_5O_{17}$ in orthorhombic ($Pnmm$, SG: 58) symmetry with several high-symmetry k -points $\Gamma(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)$, $X(0.5, 0.0, 0.0)$, $S(0.5, 0.5, 0.0)$, $Y(0.0, 0.5, 0.0)$, $Z(0.0, 0.0, 0.5)$, $U(0.5, 0.0, 0.5)$, $R(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$, and $T(0.0, 0.5, 0.5)$ ³⁹. The red lines highlight the high symmetry k -path and (b) the calculated electronic band structure along the high symmetry k -paths for $Sr_5Nb_5O_{17}$ using PBE functional. Here, the dotted line corresponds to the Fermi level, the internal band gap (E_g^{int}) is 2.30 eV, and the occupied part of conduction (ΔE_{CB}) is 0.63 eV. (c) Average real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function and (d) absorption spectra of $Sr_5Nb_5O_{17}$ when both interband and intraband transitions are accounted for. The crystal structure of $Sr_5Nb_5O_{17}$ is shown as an inset.

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In summary, our comprehensive investigation into the optical properties of gapped metals reveals significant insights into their potential role as transparent conductors. By investigating the intricate interplay of Drude contribution and the internal band gap, we have categorized gapped metals into three distinct types, each with unique optical characteristics: (i) those with strong intraband absorption in the visible range, (ii) those with strong interband absorption in the visible range, and (iii) those with optimal carrier concentration and optimal internal band gap. For the first category, we analyzed CaN_2 and found that large free carrier concentration results in strong band-to-band transitions and large unscreened plasma frequency, reducing materials transparency. These results demonstrate that a large internal gap in gapped metals is insufficient for achieving transparency and that this type of materials is not attractive for transparent conductor applications but may have other optoelectronic applications. The second category, represented by $NbCoSb$ and $SrNbO_3$, also shows strong absorption in the visible range due to the superposition of strong interband transitions or large free carrier concentrations. This type of materials highlights that a small internal gap can or intraband transition in the principal conduction

215 band can make materials unsuitable for transparent conductor application. Lastly, we considered
216 $\text{Sr}_5\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{17}$, which has optimal carrier concentration and internal band gap. We acknowledge that other
217 essential factors, such as electronic transport, defects, and mechanical properties, contribute
218 significantly to the design and performance of transparent gapped metals. Although this study primarily
219 focuses on plasma frequencies and internal band gaps, the crucial role of these factors underscores the
220 need for a holistic approach in future design and investigation of these materials. This work thus sets
221 a strong foundation for further comprehensive studies, advancing our understanding and design of
222 transparent gapped metals and potentially unlocking their full potential in a range of optoelectronic
223 applications.

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225 **Supplementary information:**

226 See the supplementary information for details on methods, average real and imaginary parts of the
227 dielectric functions for CaN_2 [Figure S1], NbCoSb [Figure S2], SrNbO_3 [Figure S3], and $\text{Sr}_5\text{Nb}_5\text{O}_{17}$ [Figure
228 S4], and sensitivity of the computed results to different exchange-correlation functionals (Figure S5 and
229 Table S1).

230

231 The authors thank the "ENSEMBLE³ - Centre of Excellence for nanophotonics, advanced materials and
232 novel crystal growth-based technologies" project (GA No. MAB/2020/14) carried out within the
233 International Research Agendas programme of the Foundation for Polish Science co-financed by the
234 European Union under the European Regional Development Fund and the European Union's Horizon
235 2020 research and innovation programme Teaming for Excellence (GA. No. 857543) for support of this
236 work. We gratefully acknowledge Poland's high-performance computing infrastructure PLGrid (HPC
237 Centers: ACK Cyfronet AGH) for providing computer facilities and support within computational grant
238 no. PLG/2022/015458.

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240 **AUTHOR DECLARATIONS**

241 **Conflict of Interest**

242 The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

243

244 **Author Contributions**

245 **Muhammad Rizwan Khan:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (lead);
246 Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal).

247 **Harshan Reddy Gopidi:** Data curation (supporting); Formal analysis (supporting); Investigation
248 (supporting); Methodology (equal); Validation (supporting); Writing – original draft (supporting).

249 **Oleksandr I. Malyi:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (supporting);
250 Methodology (equal); Validation (supporting); Writing – review & editing (equal); Project
251 administration (lead); Supervision (lead).

252

253 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

254 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
255 reasonable request.

256

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